

The Role of E-Commerce in Improving Customer Satisfaction

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How to cite this paper: H. Bhaskar Shetty | Ms. Sowmya L "The Role of E-Commerce in Improving Customer Satisfaction" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-4, June 2019, pp.802-807, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd23904.pdf>

IJTSRD23904

ABSTRACT

The cut-throat competition in E-commerce has forced the companies to focus on providing customer satisfaction and gain customer loyalty. Thus, putting up long term customer relationships through customer satisfaction is one of the pivotal foundation key factors for successful marketing, including online marketing. This research work makes an attempt to examine the role of e-commerce in building customer satisfaction and its importance to maintain loyalty in consumers. However, the study indicates that there is a progressive trend in increasing awareness and its utilities. By the study we can understand that global access, 24 hours availability, convenience, increase product information are some of the ways to enhance customer satisfaction as well as the drawback experienced by the respondents is the fear of payment security in e-commerce. The paper was with objectives of knowing the awareness, loyalty and the attitude towards online marketing.

Keywords: E-commerce, online marketing, customer satisfaction, consumer loyalty

INTRODUCTION

The term electronic commerce (e-commerce) was originated back in 1960's. This e-commerce made a drastic change in business world. E-commerce has become the most popular methods of making money. People buy online as they are benefited with lower price, accessibility, wider choice etc., even business sell online because of higher margin, lower cost of goods sold inventory management and so on. The E-commerce market in India is increasing in size at a rapid pace.

- Customer satisfaction elevates customer loyalty.
- Customer satisfaction reduces advertisement cost as there is word of mouth publicity.
- Customer satisfaction is a factor that helps you stand out of the competition.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Meaning of e-commerce and customer satisfaction

E-commerce is the combination of communication and information sharing technology which is facilitated by an electronic medium to do business activity and achieve business objective.

Customer satisfaction means the degree to which a customer is happy with their trade experience with the company. It measures how well a firm is able to meet their customer's expectations. Customer satisfaction is a key factor in marketing because a firm cannot retain its customers unless having highly satisfied customers.

Elizabeth Goldsmith and Sue L.T. McGregor (2000) analyzed the impact of e-commerce on consumers, public policy, business and education. A discussion was on public policy initiatives, research questions and ideas for future research are given. Patric Barwise (2001) reported that probability 99 % of e-commerce today is done using PCs either desktops or Laptops. For B2B e-commerce this is not easily possible to change for B2C e-commerce however, things will be more complex, there will be wider range of relevant media including interactive digital TV and a range of mobile and

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Better internet connectivity, better technology, greater access to smart phones and other mobile devices are the drivers for this growth. Various initiatives by government of India like Digital India, Make in India, Startup-India and Skill India provide greater inputs to the e-commerce industry in the country. The e-commerce online shopping is not only improving in terms of buyers and retail transaction, but also improving in terms of its stretch out and coverage. The introduction of e-commerce has seen a sensational clash on the traditional ways of doing business. It is a new trend in the world of commerce or business. E-commerce will become an essential element in every business and everywhere in our life shortly. It built a situation in the economy where all the business must get them in e-commerce either the business is big or small, or else they have to lose the market or quit. The e-commerce gradually changing the way you shop, learn, interact and transact business. In the emerging global economy e-commerce and e-business have progressively become essential aspect of business strategy and also in economic development.

REASONS WHY CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IS IMPORTANT

- Preserving satisfied customer is cheaper than acquiring new ones.
- Customer satisfaction is more significant than price.
- Customer satisfaction keeps your brand front of the competitors.
- Customer satisfaction aid for customer retention.

wireless service there will be huge difference between different consumer's ownership tools and access technology. Some will have broadband access and others may not have digital communication at all. Jackie Gilbert Bette Ann Stead (2001) reviewed the incredible growth of electronic commerce (e-commerce) and presented ethical issues that have emerged. Security concerns, spamming, websites that do not carry an "advertising" label, cyber squatters, online marketing to children, conflicts of interest, manufacturers competing with intermediaries online and "dinosaurs" were considered. Diana Oblinger (2001) reported that one is that education and continuous learning have become so vital in all societies that the demands for distance and open learning will increase. As the availability of the Internet expands as computing devices become cheaper and an energy requirements and form factors shrink, learning will become more popular. Prithviraj Dasgupta and Kasturi Sengupta (2002) reported that the recent growth of Internet Infrastructure and Introduction of economic reforms in the Insurance sector have opened up the monopolistic Indian Insurance market to competition from foreign alliances. Although the focus of e-commerce has been predominantly on business to consumer (B2C) applications the emphasis is now shifting towards business to business (B2B) applications. The Insurance Industry gives an appropriate model that combines both B2C and B2B applications.

James Christopher (2004) examined all the best elements of ecommerce do not guarantee consumers will visit or remain loyal. But looking at what they want and their satisfaction levels of other well established e-tailors such as Amazon and eBay who have already invested significant resources to understand what consumer's needs, wants and desires. Possibly it would be helpful to remove these established pure players since they have been and continue to be highly successful as retain high marks for customer satisfaction.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the awareness of E-Commerce in customers.
- To analyze the attitude of customers towards E-Commerce.
- To find out the how well E-Commerce satisfying customers.

METHODOLOGY

DATA COLLECTION

The study was conducted using random sampling method. The study was based on both primary data and secondary data. The Primary Data had been collected through structured questionnaire. The Secondary data had been collected from journals, books and magazines for the study. The size of the sample have been approximated to respondents who are customers presently purchasing products using E-Commerce. In this study Random sampling method is used. Sampling technique is simple random sample method. The sampling size refers to the number of elements to be chosen from the population to conduct sample. For this study sample size was 80.

DATA ANALYSIS

TABLE-1 GENDER - WISE CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS

Gender	Respondents	Percentage
Male	59	73.75%
Female	21	26.25%

(Source: Primary data)

1: INTERPRETATION

In the study, more than half of the respondents were male and remaining are female respondents. In the whole sample respondent population 73.75% were male respondents and remaining 26.25% were female respondents.

TABLE-2 AGE - WISE CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS

Age	Respondents	Percentage
18-29 years	44	55%
30-39 years	24	30%
40-49 years	9	11.25%
Above 50 years	3	3.75%

(Source: Primary data)

2: INTERPRETATION

The above figure represents that the classification of respondents based on their age. There were 55% respondents whose age is between 18-29 years, 30% respondents whose age between 30-39 years, 11.25% respondents whose age between 40-49 years and 3.75% respondents above 50 years.

TABLE-3 EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS

Education qualification	Respondents	Percentage
SSLC	11	13.75%
PUC	18	22.5%
Graduation	42	52.5%
Post Graduation	9	11.25%

(Source: Primary data)

3: INTERPRETATION

The chart represents that 53% of respondents are graduates, 22% of respondents are PUC, 14% of respondents are SSLC and rest 11% of respondents are post graduates. Majority of the respondents are graduates.

TABLE-4 OCCUPATION OF RESPONDENTS

Occupation	Respondents	Percentage
Student	41	51.25%
Business	20	25%
House wife	13	16.25%
Employee	6	7.5%

(Source: Primary data)

4: INTERPRETATION

The figure shows that 51% of respondents are students, 25% of respondents are business people, 16% of respondents are house wives and only 8% of respondents are employees. It means the using populations of e-commerce are students.

TABLE-5 MARITAL STATUS OF RESPONDENTS

Marital status	Respondents	Percentage
Married	22	27.5%
Single	58	72.5%

(Source: Primary data)

5: INTERPRETATION

The above chart shows that 72.5% of the respondent population are single and rest 27.5% of the respondent population are married. It represents that there is an influence of marital status in the usage of e-commerce.

TABLE-6 E-COMMERCE AWARENESS

Since when you are aware of e-commerce	Respondents	Percentage
1-5 years	74	92.5%
5-10 years	6	7.5%
>10 years	0	0%
I don't know	0	0%

(Source: Primary data)

6: INTERPRETATION

The above chart represents that 92.5% of respondents' population are aware of e-commerce since 1-5 years. Among the whole sample population, 7.5% of them were aware of e-commerce since 10 years. There were no respondents who were not aware of e-commerce.

TABLE-7 TIME PERIOD OF USAGE OF E-COMMERCE

Since how many years are you using e-commerce?	Respondents	Percentage
1-5 years	42	52.5%
5-10 years	4	5%
>10 years	0	0%
Not yet used	34	42.5%

(Source: Primary data)

7: INTERPRETATION

The above chart represents that 52.5% of respondents are using e-commerce since 5 years. There are 5% of respondents who are using since 10 years and 42.5% of the respondents have not yet used e-commerce till today.

TABLE-8 PURPOSE OF USING E-COMMERCE

Purpose for use e-commerce is	Respondents	Percentage
Personal use (BUYING)	72	90%
Business use (SELLING)	8	10%
Both personal and business use	0	0%

(Source: Primary data)

8: INTERPRETATION

The chart shows that 90% of the respondent population is making use of online commerce or e-commerce for personal use. Rest 10% of population is making use of e-commerce for business purpose. There are no respondents who are making use of online commerce both for personal and business purpose.

TABLE-9 BENEFITS OF E-COMMERCE TO CONSUMERS

How do you think e-commerce is benefited to consumers	Respondents	Percentage
24/7 accessibility	0	0%
Broadens consumers choice	0	0%
Comparative price	0	0%
All the above	80	100%

(Source: Primary data)

9: INTERPRETATION

The total respondent population (100%) has chosen all the above options. It means that consumers are benefited with 24/7 accessibility, broadens consumers choice and comparative price.

TABLE-10 BENEFITS OF E-COMMERCE TO BUSINESS

How do you think e-commerce helps the business	Respondents	Percentage
Smoothens business	16	20%
Less startup, transaction and inventory cost	8	10%
Global reach	44	55%
All the above	12	15%

(Source: Primary data)

10: INTERPRETATION

The chart shows that 55% of sample population's opinion is global reach which is a major benefit by e-commerce to the business. 20% of respondents say that e-commerce benefits the business by smoothening the business. 10% of respondents say it reduces the cost to the business. Remaining 15% of respondents say all of those options are the benefits of e-commerce to the business.

TABLE-11 THE EXTENT TO WHICH E-COMMERCE MEETS NEEDS OF CONSUMERS

do products in e-commerce meet need	Respondents	Percentage
Badly	6	7.5%
Fine	10	12.5%
Well	24	30%
Very well	40	50%

(Source: Primary data)

11: INTERPRETATION

The above chart shows that 50% of population says that products meet their needs very well. 30% of the respondents say that products meet their needs well. 12.5% of respondents say that products are fine in meeting their needs and 7.5% of the population says that products meet their needs badly.

TABLE-12 CLEAR PRE-INFORMATION ABOUT GOODS AND SERVICES

Adequate and clear product information	Respondents	Percentage
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Disagree	12	15%
Neutral	6	7.5%
Agree	42	52.5%
Strongly agree	20	25%

(Source: Primary data)

12: INTERPRETATION

The above chart shows that 52.5% of respondents agree, 25% of respondents strongly agree, 7.5% of them are neutral and 15% of respondents disagree with the statements that pre-information is adequate.

TABLE-13 E-COMMERCE MADE IT EASY TO HANDLE PURCHASES

The e-commerce made easy to handle my issues.	Respondents	Percentage
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Disagree	2	2.5%
Neutral	8	10%
Agree	58	72.5%
Strongly agree	12	15%

(Source: Primary data)

13: INTERPRETATION

The chart shows that 72.5% of the population agrees that e-commerce made it easy to handle the purchase issues. 15% of the population strongly agrees, 10% of them are neutral and 2.5% of them disagree by saying that e-commerce made it easy to handle purchase issues.

TABLE-14 PRICE OF PRODUCTS ARE COMPETITIVE

The price of product or services on website is competitive	Respondents	Percentage
Strongly disagree	4	5%
Disagree	10	12.5%
Neutral	14	17.5%
Agree	40	50%
Strongly agree	12	15%

(Source: Primary data)

14: INTERPRETATION

The above chart shows that 50% respondents in the sample population agree that the prices of products are competitive in e-commerce. Among the population 15% respondents strongly agree, 17.5% of them are neutral, 12.5% of them disagree and 5% of them strongly disagree that the prices of the product are competitive on e-commerce.

TABLE-15 PRODUCTS PRICES ARE CHEAP

Price of goods in internet is cheaper.	Respondents	Percentage
Strongly disagree	20	25%
Disagree	6	7.5%
Neutral	8	10%
Agree	46	57.5%
Strongly agree	0	0%

(Source: Primary data)

15: INTERPRETATION

The above graph shows that 57.5% respondents agree that product prices are cheaper. 25% respondents strongly disagree, 10% respondents are neutral, 7.5% of the respondents disagree that the price of products are cheaper.

TABLE-16 BILLING AND SHIPPING INFORMATION ARE SIMPLE

Billing and shipping information is clear	Respondents	Percentage
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Disagree	16	20%
Neutral	32	40%
Agree	20	25%
Strongly agree	12	15%

(Source: Primary data)

16: INTERPRETATION

The chart shows that 25% of the population agrees that billing and shipping information are simple to understand. 15% respondents of the population strongly agree, 40% of them are neutral and 20% of them disagree for the question billing and shipping information are clear and easy to

TABLE-17 PRODUCT PERFORMANCE AS EXPECTED

Product performed as I expected	Respondents	Percentage
Strongly disagree	16	20%
Disagree	24	30%
Neutral	24	30%
Agree	16	20%
Strongly agree	0	0%

17: INTERPRETATION

The above chart says that 30% respondents of the population have shown disagree and neutral response towards the question whether the products performed as they expected. 20% of respondents said that they agree and remaining 20% of them say that they strongly disagree for the statement products performed as they expected.

TABLE-18 SHOPPING IN E-COMMERCE IS TIME SAVING

Shopping in e-commerce is time saving	Respondents	Percentage
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Disagree	0	0%
Neutral	4	5%
Agree	64	80%
Strongly agree	12	15%

(Source: Primary data)

18: INTERPRETATION

The above chart shows that 80% respondents of the sample population agree that e-commerce is time saving. 15% of the respondents strongly agreed and 5% of them showed neutral response for the statement that e-commerce is time saving.

TABLE-19 HOW RESPONSIVE IS E-COMMERCE TO CUSTOMER QUESTIONS

How responsive is e-commerce to customers	Respondents	Percentage
Irresponsive	10	12.5%
Usually responsive	56	70%
Very responsive	14	17.5%

(Source: Primary data)

19: INTERPRETATION

The above chart shows that 70% of them say that e-commerce is usually responsive. 17.5% of them say that they are very responsive and remaining 12.5% of them say that the e-commerce is irresponsible for the queries asked by the customers or consumers.

TABLE-20 AFTER SALES SERVICE OF E-COMMERCE

After sales service of e-commerce	Respondents	Percentage
Very bad	0	0%
Poor	8	10%
Fair	66	82.5%
Good	6	7.5%
Excellent	0	0%

(Source: Primary data)

20: INTERPRETATION

The above graph shows that 82.5% respondents say that after sales service is fair. 10% respondents of the sample population say poor after sales service. 7.5% respondents say that after sales service is good in online or e-commerce.

TABLE-21 EASY TO CANCEL ORDER OR RETURN GOODS PURCHASED

Easy to cancel order or return goods purchased	Respondents	Percentage
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Disagree	18	22.5%
Neutral	24	30%
Agree	34	42.5%
Strongly agree	4	5%

(Source: Primary data)

21: INTERPRETATION

The above graph shows 42.5% respondents are agreeing that it is easy to cancel order or return goods purchased through online. 30% respondents are neutral, 22.5% respondents disagree and rest 5% respondents strongly agree that it is easy to cancel order and return the goods purchased.

TABLE-22 E-COMMERCE ELEMİNATES MIDDLEMEN

E-commerce eliminates middlemen	Respondents	Percentage
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Disagree	12	15%
Neutral	58	72.5%
Agree	10	12.5%
Strongly agree	0	0%

(Source: Primary data)

22: INTERPRETATION

The above graph shows that 72.5% of the respondents (58 respondents) gave neutral response, 15% respondents disagree and 12.5% respondents agree that e-commerce eliminates middlemen.

TABLE-23 FREQUENCY OF PURCHASE ANNUALLY

Frequently of purchase	Respondents	Percentage
Purchase once annually	8	10%
2-5 purchase	40	50%
6-10 purchase	20	25%
11 and above purchases	12	15%

(Source: Primary data)

23: INTERPRETATION

The above graph shows 50% respondents of the population usually purchase 2-5 times annually. 25% respondents purchase 6-10 times annually. 15% of them purchase 11 and above times annually and 10% of them purchase once annually.

TABLE-24 LIKELY TO BUY AGAIN

How likely to buy again	Respondents	Percentage
Not likely at all	0	0%
Not likely	36	45%
Neutral	0	0%
Likely	44	55%
Very likely	0	0%

(Source: Primary data)

24: INTERPRETATION

The above chart shows that 55% respondents are likely to buy again through online or e-commerce. Remaining 45% respondents have said that they are not likely to buy again through e-commerce.

TABLE-25 HOW GOOD E-COMMERCE IS OVER TRADITIONAL COMMERCE

How good is e-commerce than traditional commerce	Respondents	Percentage
Very bad	0	0%
Poor	10	12.5%
Fair	24	30%
Good	40	50%
Excellent	6	7.5%

(Source: Primary data)

25: INTERPRETATION

The above chart represents that 50% respondents say that e-commerce is good over traditional commerce. 30% respondents are saying that e-commerce is fair enough than traditional commerce. Among remaining 7.5% respondents excellent and 12.5% respondents say poor about how good e-commerce is over traditional commerce.

TABLE-26 LIKELY TO RECOMMEND

Likely to recommend	Respondents	Percentage
Not likely at all	6	7.5%
Not likely	16	20%
Neutral	32	40%
Likely	14	17.5%
Very likely	12	15%

(Source: Primary data)

26: INTERPRETATION

The above graph shows that 40% of the population are neutral towards likely to recommend. 20% respondents are not likely, 17.5% respondents are likely, 15% respondents are very likely, 7.5% respondents are not likely at all towards question likely to recommend.

TABLE-27 INCREASE IN E-COMMERCE USING POPULATION

Increase in e-commerce using population	Respondents	Percentage
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Disagree	0	0%
Neutral	4	5%
Agree	64	80%
Strongly agree	12	15%

(Source: Primary data)

27: INTERPRETATION

The above graph shows that 80% respondents of the sample population agree that using population of e-commerce has increased over years. 15% of the respondents strongly agreed and 5% of them show neutral response for the statement that using population of e-commerce has increased over years.

TABLE-28 SATISFACTION WITH PURCHASE EXPERIENCE

How satisfied with purchase experience	Respondents	Percentage
Very dissatisfied	0	0%
Dissatisfied	14	17.5%
Neutral	26	32.5%
Satisfied	24	30%
Very satisfied	16	20%

(Source: Primary data)

28: INTERPRETATION

The above graph shows that 30% respondents are satisfied, 32.5% respondents are neutral, 20% of them are very satisfied and rest 17.5% of the respondents are dissatisfied with the purchase experience through online or e-commerce.

TABLE-3.29 QUALITY OF TRADING THROUGH ONLINE

How would you rate the overall quality of buying and selling through online	Respondents	Percentage
Very bad	6	7.5%
Poor	8	10%
Fair	12	15%
Good	24	30%
Excellent	30	37.5%

(Source: Primary data)

29: INTERPRETATION

The above graph shows that 37.5% respondents say that the quality of trading through online is excellent. 30% respondents say quality of trading online is good. Among remaining 15% respondents say it is fair and 10% of them say that it has poor quality. Rest 7.5% of them said it has very bad quality of trading through online.

TABLE-30 5 STAR SCALE RATING FOR E-COMMERCE

Five star scale rating for e-commerce.	Respondents	Percentage
Very dissatisfied	0	0%
Dissatisfied	6	7.5%
Neutral	30	37.5%
Satisfied	44	55%
Very satisfied	0	0%

(Source: Primary data)

30: INTERPRETATION

The above chart says that 55% of respondents population are satisfied buying through e-commerce. 37.5% of respondents are showing neutral response and 7.5% respondents were dissatisfied.

CONCLUSION

Online shopping is becoming more popular day by day with the increase in usage of WORLD WIDE WEB as www. E-commerce is continuously improving and becoming more and more pivotal to business as technology continues to advance and is something that should be taken advantage of and implemented. From the inspection of the e-commerce, the possibilities have become endless for both businesses and consumers.

From the previous data analysis project can be concluded that the awareness among people have increased as well as most of them are making use of online shopping, product information cancelling and returning of goods are clear and simple to understand and more than half of the respondents are satisfied with e-commerce.

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